

Detection of Spatially Extended Objects in Clutter

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Abstract—Range-spread Doppler-spread signals in interference are readily discernable via the application of classical algorithms and architectures presented by Van Trees [1], and more recently by Kay [2] and others. However, when these returns emanate from stationary objects, the Generalized Inner Product (GIP) offers a unique tool for detection and discrimination processing. This paper offers insight into how the GIP may be applied to optimize the detection of spatially extended fixed objects in clutter.

1 INTRODUCTION

Stationary fixed targets on the ground can only be detected by an airborne radar if their returns sufficiently exceed those from the ground (clutter). A technique has been developed that can achieve significantly better detection for extended targets in clutter. This generalized inner product (GIP) based approach assumes limited knowledge of the target of interest, including its orientation. The GIP has been previously applied in signal processing to improve the performance of adaptive radar operating in nonhomogeneous clutter [3 - 5]. Analysis has been accomplished for targets whose parameters are known perfectly and for targets whose parameters are only known approximately.

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE GIP BASED DETECTOR

2.1. Radar Data Matrices

The GIP is used to discriminate range-spread returns from strong surface clutter in airborne radar. Consider a GIP based detector in which a signal arrives at a radar receiver channel. A preprocessing unit receives analog signals, down converts to an intermediate frequency, digitizes them, and applies traditional radar signal processing to yield baseband frequency, complex-valued, digital in-phase-and-quadrature radar signal samples that correspond to each range cell for each transmitted pulse (range-pulse data). Preprocessing also includes digital pulse compression. Denote the radar signal samples at the k^{th} range cell and n^{th} pulse as $x_k(n)$ for $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$, where N is the number of pulses in one CPI and K is the number of range cells of interest.

The received radar signal includes target and clutter returns together with additive noise. Clutter returns are a correlated form of interference. Mathematically, the received radar signal at the n^{th} sampling time instant can be expressed as

$$x_k(n) = t_k(n) + c_k(n) + n_k(n), \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad (1)$$

where $\{t_k(n)\}$, $\{c_k(n)\}$ and $\{n_k(n)\}$ denote the target signal, surface (ground or sea) clutter, and noise components, respectively. Both clutter and noise are assumed to be stationary, ergodic, zero-mean, Gaussian stochastic processes, and independent to each other. The radar signal can be rewritten in vector form:

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{t}_k + \mathbf{c}_k + \mathbf{n}_k. \quad (2)$$

Thus, the range-pulse data received in one CPI for K range cells can be expressed in matrix form as

$$\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1 \quad \mathbf{x}_2 \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{x}_K]. \quad (3)$$

The range-pulse data matrix has a dimension of $N \times K$.

Given an observation data matrix \mathbf{X} , the radar detection problem reduces to choosing between one of the following two hypotheses:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0: \quad \mathbf{X} &= \mathbf{C} + \mathbf{N} \\ H_1: \quad \mathbf{X} &= \mathbf{T} + \mathbf{C} + \mathbf{N} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{T} , \mathbf{C} , and \mathbf{N} are $N \times K$ matrices.

A discrete Fourier transform with a low sidelobe window (weighted DFT) is applied to the signal samples for each range cell, which converts the range-pulse data matrix to a range-Doppler data matrix:

$$\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{X}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(1,1) & \mathbf{x}(1,2) & \dots & \mathbf{x}(1,K) \\ \mathbf{x}(2,1) & \mathbf{x}(2,2) & \dots & \mathbf{x}(2,K) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}(N,1) & \mathbf{x}(N,2) & \dots & \mathbf{x}(N,K) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathcal{F}(\cdot)$ denotes the column-by-column weighted DFT, and the indices (n, k) in $\mathbf{x}(n,k)$ denote the n^{th} Doppler cell and the k^{th} range cell, respectively. The range-Doppler data matrix includes $K \times N$ range-Doppler cells. Similarly, we can respectively express the component matrices as

$$\mathcal{T} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{T}), \quad \mathcal{C} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{C}), \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{N} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{N}). \quad (6)$$

In the range-Doppler data matrix, clutter (and noise) could appear in all these range-Doppler cells, while the target only appears in a very limited number

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of cells determined by its range-Doppler trace. Assume that a radar is located at $(0, 0, H)$ on the Z-axis where H is the altitude of the radar. The radar velocity vector \mathbf{v} (speed = V_R) is parallel with the Y-axis. The surface of the earth is assumed to be flat. The Doppler frequency for a stationary scatterer located at a point $P(x, y, 0)$ on the earth's surface can be expressed as

$$f_c = \frac{2V_R}{\lambda} \cos \theta \sin \alpha = \frac{2V_R \sqrt{R^2 - H^2}}{\lambda R} \sin \alpha, \quad (7)$$

where R denotes the slant range, θ is the depression (grazing) angle, and α is the azimuth angle, counterclockwise, starting from the X-axis (the x-axis represents broadside). Therefore, there is a "one-to one" mapping relationship between the Doppler frequency and azimuth angle for a given range R . The surface clutter will spread over extended range-Doppler cells.

2.2. Target Templates

A key for the GIP based detector is to integrate the over-resolved target power over as many range-Doppler cells as possible and suppress clutter. Therefore, the range-Doppler profiles (indices) of targets with different orientations, and at different locations, are required. For this purpose, a database of target templates including the shapes (structures) of targets of interest is required. If the shape and size of a target is approximately known, a corresponding target template can be used. The database also includes several standard templates for the case that little or no knowledge about the target is known. A general requirement to all templates is that they must be big enough so that their range-Doppler spectrum spreads over multiple range-Doppler cells. Two standard templates are recognized: a circular ring for linear (wire-like) targets and a circular disk for planar targets. Here, an object is called linear if its section size is much smaller than the whole, such as with wires and pipes. The planar targets are general extended objects.

A range-Doppler index calculator produces the range-Doppler indices for the selected target template with each specified parameter set $\Theta = \{\text{target parameters, radar parameters}\}$, required to form GIP images. The target parameters usually include information about the target such as position (range, azimuth, etc.), orientation, and radial speed, etc. The target position can be defined by a reference point (for example, the geographical center) on the target. The radar parameters include the radar system and geometrical parameters such as radar wavelength, moving speed, and altitude. Fig. 1 shows an example for a circular-ring with radius r lying on the ground. The center of circle is at $C(x_0, y_0)$ with

$$\begin{cases} x_0 = \sqrt{R_c^2 - H^2} \cos \alpha_c \\ y_0 = \sqrt{R_c^2 - H^2} \sin \alpha_c \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where R_c is the radar slant range, and α_c is the azimuthal angle, measured from the X-axis counterclockwise.

Figure 1: Scenario for the calculation of range-Doppler indices of a circular ring on the ground.

The coordinates of the circular object can be described in the following parametric equations:

$$\begin{cases} x = x_0 + r \cos \phi \\ y = y_0 + r \sin \phi \end{cases} \quad \text{for } \phi = 0 \sim 2\pi \quad (9)$$

The corresponding Doppler frequency can be calculated using the previously given equation, with the azimuth angle being $\alpha = \tan^{-1}(y/x)$. The slant range from a point on the circular ring to the radar is $R = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + H^2}$. Thus, given the center location and radius, the range-Doppler trace of a circular ring can be completely determined. Therefore, its range-Doppler indices can be found by quantization. A stationary object on the ground has a spectral nature similar to that of the ground clutter from the same location. In contrast to the extended surface clutter, a linear object only appears in limited range-Doppler cells, which are determined by the object's shape and location. Assume that the range-Doppler trace of the target template spreads over N^t range-Doppler cells with the corresponding indices being $(n'_1, k'_1), (n'_2, k'_2), \dots, (n'_{N^t}, k'_{N^t})$. Define the index set of the target template as

$$\Omega_t = \{(n'_1, k'_1), (n'_2, k'_2), \dots, (n'_{N^t}, k'_{N^t})\}. \quad (10)$$

Obviously, Ω_t varies with the parameter set Θ . The results can easily be applied to moving targets by shifting the Doppler indices according to the corresponding target Doppler frequency.

2.3. GIP Based Detector

Generally, the range-Doppler index set Ω is calculated for a set of specific parameters and used to select the range-Doppler entries from the stored range-Doppler data matrix. The data vector under test can be formed by extracting entries belonging to the index set Ω_i :

$$\mathbf{x}_o = \text{Vec}[\{\mathbf{x}(n,k), (n,k) \in \Omega_i\}], \quad (11)$$

where $\text{Vec}[\cdot]$ denotes the vectorizing operation that leads to a column ($N' \times 1$) vector.

The GIP test statistics can be expressed as

$$GIP = \mathbf{x}_o^H \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{x}_o, \quad (12)$$

where

$$\mathbf{R} = E[\mathbf{x}_o \mathbf{x}_o^H | H_0] \quad (13)$$

is the covariance matrix of the test data vector in the absence of a target.

In practice, the true covariance matrix of the test data vector is unknown and can usually be estimated from training data. Assume that we have M training data matrices \mathbf{X}_m for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$. After the weighted DFT, we obtain the M range-Doppler training data matrices $\mathbf{x}_m = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{X}_m)$. Extracting the entries belonging to the index set Ω_i , we can form M training data vectors: $\mathbf{x}_m = \text{Vec}[\{\mathbf{x}_m(n,k), (n,k) \in \Omega_i\}]$, for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$.

Assuming that all training data vectors are Gaussian and independent, identically distributed (iid) with the covariance matrix \mathbf{R} , the maximum-likelihood estimate of \mathbf{R} can be expressed as

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \mathbf{x}_m \mathbf{x}_m^H. \quad (14)$$

The GIP test statistics becomes

$$GIP = \mathbf{x}_o^H \hat{\mathbf{R}}^{-1} \mathbf{x}_o. \quad (15)$$

3 SIMULATION RESULTS

3.1. Target and Radar Parameters

A radar signal modeling and simulation tool [6] is used to simulate the radar signals (target, clutter, and noise). In this example, the target is a circular-shaped object on the ground, as shown in Figure 1. In this scenario and coordinate system the XOY plane is at the surface of

the ground with the origin at the nadir point of the radar, which is flying level along the Y-axis at altitude H . A circular-shaped object with radius r lies on the ground. The center of the circular object is at $C(x_o, y_o)$. This object may be a short conductive O-ring. For modeling, the object is divided into many small segments. Each segment is short enough so that it can be approximated as a circular cylinder and the far-field condition is met. An L-band radar with a bandwidth of 250 MHz was modeled. The platform altitude was 600 meters and the platform velocity was 50 meters/second. The clutter background was assumed to be farm land.

3.2. One Dimensional GIP

The position and size of a ring-like target can be determined by three parameters: radius, azimuth, and slant range. This subsection presents the GIP output as a function of one unknown parameter, assuming the other two parameters are known in the template.

Case 1: Assume the radius and azimuth of the template match those of the target. Figure 2 shows the GIP outputs as a function of slant range. It is shown that the GIP peaks sharply at the true target range.

Case 2: Assume the range and azimuth of the center of the object in the template match those of the target. Figure 3 shows the corresponding GIP outputs as a function of the radius of ring.

Case 3: Assume that the radius of the circular template and its center range match the true values. Fig. 4 shows the GIP output as a function of azimuth angle of the ring center. It is shown that the GIP also peaks at the true azimuth of target.

Figure 2. GIP as a function of slant range.

Figure 3. GIP as a function of radius.

Figure 4. GIP as a function of azimuth

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented a GIP detector in range-Doppler that offers a unique tool for detection and discrimination of spatially extended fixed objects in heavy clutter. The GIP detector is also applicable to the detection of slowing moving objects.

For an airborne radar, the training data matrices $\{X_m\}$ can be obtained from adjacent coherent processing intervals (CPIs) during the flight. Historical data that excludes targets can be used as training data also. GIP images can be formed by varying any two parameters in the parameter set Θ [7]. Thus, multiple GIP images can be formed. The GIP images can also be used for target detection and discrimination processing.

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